

PROSPECTS OF COOPERATION WITH THE PUBLIC IN THE ACTIVITIES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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ABSTRACT

Today, taking into account that the special powers of the internal affairs bodies are applied to all spheres of social life, the issue of cooperation with the public is gaining urgent importance for the state and society. The article presents an analysis of their national customs, legal system and state administration, strategies and tactics of the police in the fight against crime in foreign countries, problems of cooperation of the internal affairs bodies with the public, and offers suggestions.

Realization and protection of human rights and legal interests is one of the main tasks of every democratic legal state. In this case, it is important to organize work through re-communication with the public, along with the powers of state bodies, organizations and institutions provided for by law.

In this regard, law enforcement agencies, especially internal affairs agencies, based on their characteristics in crime prevention, the issue of cooperation with the public is gaining urgent importance for the state and society. Because it is no secret that the special powers of internal affairs bodies are applied to all spheres of social life [7].

From the second half of the 20th century, mainly in the 80s and 90s, the police system was radically reformed in many countries. Reforms aimed at changing from the "observant" structure to a socially oriented "community policing" (policing at the service of the population) idea that communicates closely with the population and serves their interests. These changes in the police system, first of all, were turned into activities aimed at the prevention of crime in cooperation with civil and civil society institutions.

In particular, crime and public disorder, which escalated in the countries of the USA, Japan, Western Europe, and Asia at that time, led to "crisis" measures by police authorities, in particular to strengthen legal measures, to increase the number of police officers, to further expand their social guarantees, to improve the reputation of the police through the media. The efforts to promote the uplifting agitation did not show their effectiveness sufficiently. Among the population, on the contrary, such measures raised their anger and created a mood of dissatisfaction and mistrust towards them.

Since the idea of "community policing" embodies the most advanced theory and practice of policing aimed at radically renewing the activities of public order maintenance bodies, the

purpose of the activities of police bodies integrated into society in countries that have used it in their experience is not only to fight crime, but primarily through close cooperation with the population. crime prevention consists of preventing crimes.

The issue of professional training in the police system based on the partnership doctrine was also fundamentally revised. In particular, in the police academies of the USA, Europe and Japan, modern socio-psychological programs have been introduced to train police officers to effectively communicate with citizens of various categories (victims, witnesses, mentally ill, drug addicts, etc.) [2]. Later this practice gave the following effective results. In particular, the reduction of re-appeals and stress situations in the police profession led to an increase in public confidence in the police and the public's desire to cooperate with the police[3].

Based on the idea of "community policing", the reform has been successfully implemented in different countries. The reason for this diversity is reflected in the national traditions, legal system and state administration, and the specific characteristics of the strategies and tactics of the police in combating crime.

USA: A socially oriented approach. The US police system is three-tiered, i.e. local, state, federal), and the main part of the staff (60 percent) is formed in the local police, and interaction with the population is the basis of this system[4]. In the 90s of the last century, all available innovative resources were involved in the fight against crime in the United States. In particular, firstly, it was transformed into a socially oriented service working in cooperation with the population, secondly, crime prevention by uncompromisingly fighting specific types of crimes along with "soft" socially oriented activities in cooperation with the population, and thirdly, in the mass media, this doctrine was "elimination of the offense, punishment for the crime is inevitable" aimed at the formation of the opinion.

According to the US Bureau of Justice Statistics (BJS), the number of crimes has decreased in the last 10-15 years [9].

Sweden: A problem-oriented approach. We can see the effect of police activities based on the concept of "Community policing" in the prevention of crimes in the Swedish experience. Active cooperation with the population was required to implement this concept. Therefore, great attention is paid to the professionalism and social-psychological aspects of employees. In particular, these aspects include requirements such as: higher education, quality selection of personnel, good mastery of ethical standards and respect for human rights and freedoms (because "respect for the law begins with respect for the citizen"). Increasing the intellectual capacity of police officers, by increasing their salaries, affected the image of the police officer and led to an increase in his social status (reputation). It is in the Scandinavian countries that reforms were carried out based on the following law: the higher the educational index of employees and the level of culture and education, the more effective their professional activity will be.

In the experience of the Swedish police, the problem-oriented approach "problem-oriented policing" is aimed at eliminating the reasons and negative facts of the population turning to the police. According to the Swedish National Council for Crime and Prevention (BRA), globalization has introduced new types of crime as statistics. In particular, crimes related to plastic card, online credit (sale), internet harassment are among them. Therefore, we can show that, although the probability of becoming a victim of crime among the population

has increased compared to previous years, trust in the criminal justice system (police, prosecutor's office, court, JIEM and probation service) has not decreased.

France: the doctrine of "security cooperation". In the 90s of the last century, France, like other countries of the European Union, underwent reforms based on the concept of a new approach to public order, based on the principles of cooperation with the population. The idea of "community policing" was implemented in the French interpretation of "police de proximité". In this case, police activities began to provide services in the field of providing security to the population in the form of social services. Now, the police is not only a crime-fighting body, but also a peace-keeping body[5]. Mechanisms for the implementation of the idea of "closer policing" were reflected in the Law "On Security" between 1997-2002. This idea, which included coordinating the management of the national police and the gendarmerie, did not have sufficient support among the police and the population, and the reforms did not reach the final point. Since 2002, the French government has returned to the traditional "tough police" and "certain result" regime. In fact, during this period, the statistics of solving murder crimes improved significantly (in 2007 it was 88 percent). However, a big gap has appeared again between the population and the police. So, this regime once again proved that it is possible to give temporary results.

Since 2008, reforms aimed at establishing a "contract of mutual trust" between citizens and the police began. With the "social distance" between the population and the police, the state of crime in the country, that is, the statistics, did not change much.

"Partenariat pour la sécurité", i.e. "Partnership for Security", a new type of policing system launched in 2018, envisages civil society and the police jointly "creating security". Public safety is now not only the responsibility of the police, but also the responsibility of the public. In 2021, the Law "On General Security to Preserve Freedom" was adopted, aimed at expanding the legal, organizational and technical capabilities of police structures to maintain law and order in the country. This Law covered two important issues. Firstly, the powers of the National Police and Gendarmerie to use modern technical means for quick supervision while preserving the freedoms of citizens were expanded, and secondly, the police structures were given the opportunity to involve civil society in order to "create security", and this is mainly used widely in local police activities[1].

According to the French Ministry of the Interior, in 2016-2022, we can show that the indicator of 48 crimes and violations per 1000 people has been maintained for seven years. The pandemic period in 2020 is an exception[11].

Japan: the introduction of modern technology and centuries-old traditions. In this low-crime country, the police are considered to be only a government agency, and in the capital and prefectures, the traditional police system of district and district police consists of "stationary booths" ("Koban"). For example, in Tokyo, each of the 110 police units consists of 10-15 "Kobans" and performs the task of maintaining public order at the primary-local level[3]. Each police station has a "Community Liaison Board". Representatives of public organizations, local self-governance committees, administration of large settlement complexes, volunteer groups act as members of these councils.

The use of informal forms of social control, focusing on family policy in the formation of stereotypes of socially beneficial behavior, taking special measures for the resocialization of

criminals by the public are among the factors that raise the socially oriented Japanese police system to a higher level.

According to the National Police Agency, the crime rate over the past six years is the lowest in 75 years[11].

Uzbekistan: a socially oriented approach. Within the framework of the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 and the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the transformation of internal affairs bodies into a pro-people professional structure as a reliable defender of the population, their close cooperation with citizens, public organizations and the general public, mutual trust and ensuring its operation in the spirit of unity, further strengthening the rule of law, peace and tranquility in neighborhoods, residential areas and the entire country.

In this, the main emphasis was given to extensive work aimed at turning the internal affairs bodies into a socially oriented professional structure that provides timely and quality assistance to the population, and each of its employees considers serving the interests of the people as their duty.

At the same time, the requirements of the professional culture and service discipline of the employees of the Internal Affairs bodies were reworked. Now, on the basis of the principle of "For the dignity of the person", by training the employees of the internal affairs bodies to be representatives of the state with high moral and ethical qualities, loyal to their duty, patriotic and people-loving, to gain the trust of the population, to prevent the possible cases of improper behavior, abuse and corruption in the system. one of the main goals was early prevention, not creating conflict situations that negatively affect the reputation of the law enforcement system.

Reforms in the direction of professional training of employees of socially oriented internal affairs bodies were closely implemented. In particular, spiritual and educational work was systematically and continuously organized on the basis of the principle "from the educational institution to the end of the service". From September 1, 2023, the practice of continuous training of employees of crime prevention, road patrol and patrol-post service units on the "Citizens Work Module" was launched.

Also, taking into account the specific features of the service, the role of expert psychologists in the process of appointing and certifying employees of internal affairs bodies has been increased.

Cooperation of the internal affairs bodies with the public is mainly carried out by the base points of the internal affairs bodies. According to Article 15 of the Law "On Internal Affairs Bodies", the bases of internal affairs bodies are established in order to ensure the cooperation of the internal affairs bodies of the internal affairs departments (departments) of districts and cities with the public and to maintain public order in villages, villages and neighborhoods, the safety of citizens, violations is the main sub-link[6] that directly provides prevention and fight against crime.

At the same time, the issue of public cooperation in the system is implemented through public control mechanisms. By the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-10 of January 20, 2023, the Ministry of Internal Affairs and its territorial units were authorized to establish public councils, which are considered to be a consultative body that

operates on a public basis, consisting of scientists, veterans and journalists. As the main tasks of public councils:

implementation of public control over compliance with the requirements of legislative documents in the activities of internal affairs bodies, study of social opinion in the field and systematic monitoring;

to take measures to ensure that social opinion and community interests are taken into account during the development of drafts of legislative documents regulating the activities of internal affairs bodies;

It was decided to study in detail the messages published on the Internet and social networks regarding the cases of corruption in the activities of the internal affairs bodies and to communicate its results to the general public [8].

In general, we can point out that the reforms of the police system in foreign countries have different trends in each country, transforming them from a "crisis", "reprehensible" system to a "socially oriented" system. It is obvious that crime prevention and crime prevention are the main tasks of the socially oriented police system. The tactics of police work are focused on maintaining public order and fighting crime together with the public. As a result, it is clearly visible that it had a positive effect on the general indicator of crimes. However, we can see that the number of crimes committed using information technology and the Internet is increasing. In order to prevent such crimes, it is necessary to study the issue of cooperation of police authorities with other organizations.

As a result of the analysis of the experience of developed countries in the issue of cooperation of internal affairs bodies with the public in the prevention of crime, we can come to the following conclusion:

firstly, today the society (population) demands from the law enforcement body to protect human rights and freedoms in the course of its activity or exercise its powers, i.e. "Respecting the law begins with respecting the citizen";

secondly, the reforms implemented in the police structures in the world transformed them into a body operating on the basis of the idea of socially oriented "community policing" (policing at the service of the population) that communicates closely with the population from a "condemning", "crisis" structure;

thirdly, in order to "create security" in the state, police structures were given the opportunity to involve civil society. For this, the main force (personnel) was given to the lower ranks of the police;

fourthly, prevention of crimes is the most advanced way to fight them. Therefore, there have been major changes in legislation and practice aimed at developing legal and organizational mechanisms of crime prevention;

fifth, public monitoring mechanisms were widely used. In particular, the establishment of a public evaluation system of the police and its employees will first of all show the most objective assessment of the effectiveness of the reforms being implemented;

sixth, public opinion polling in police activities is used to improve the image of police authorities. As a result of the cooperation of the police and the public, it serves to identify and solve problems on the spot.

The reforms in the system of internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which began in 2016, are making many efforts to turn it into a socially oriented structure. In this regard, it is known that international standards and advanced foreign legislation and practices have been researched. The main thing is that protecting the interests of the society along with the needs of the state is one of the main goals of the system. At the same time, implementation of close cooperation with the population and the public in the activities of internal affairs bodies through various forms (official and informal) serves to increase the efficiency of the activities of internal affairs bodies.

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